

STUDY OF GROUNDWATER SCENARIO OF VADODARA CITY

Sachin B. Shah¹

Dr. Sanskriti S. Mujumdar²

Prof. Arvind S. Patel³

1. Student, M E (Civil) Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001.

Email : sachin_umreth@rediffmail.com

2. Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001.

Email: sanskritimujumdar@yahoo.co.in

3. Professor & Head, Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering,

The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001.

Email: aspatel_ced@msubaroda.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Vadodara is the third populous city of Gujarat having a highly complicated hydro geological condition. The areas have great variations in aquifer thickness. Ground water plays an important role along with the surface water to be supplied as a source of water for the Vadodara city.

It is therefore very important to study the quantity and quality of ground water condition of Vadodara City. The study of hydro geological condition is very important as far as the exploration and recharge of ground water is concerned.

Through this paper it is attempted to divide the Vadodara city into various zones as per the geo hydrological conditions.

OBJECTIVES

Following are the objectives of the research work carried out in the paper

1. To divide the Vadodara city into various zones as per litholog
2. To study Ground water quality of Vadodara city.
3. To establish relation between litholog and yield/quality of ground water
4. To prepare guide map for Vadodara city for Ground water exploration and Recharge.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED

The methodology adopted for the study is as follows:

1. Collection of lithologs of study area.
2. Collection of datas regarding quality of ground water in the area
3. Collection of data for groundwater table fluctuations.
4. Analysis of litholog data
5. Analysis of Groundwater table fluctuations.

DATA COLLETED

The basic data about the study area was collected from various offices. The Lithologs datas as well as the groundwater table fluctuations were collected from GWRDC, State Water Data Centre. The data regarding quality of ground water were collected from GWRDC, State Water Data Centre, Public Health Laboratory, VMSS, Vadodara, GWSSB, Vadodara & also from various private water testing laboratories.

INTRODUCTION :

Vadodara, located in the 22° 18' 00" N and 73° 12' 01" E, is one of the famous cities in the central part of the state of Gujarat in India. Situated on the banks of the Vishwamitri river, Vadodara is the fertile plain land between the rivers Narmada and Mahi. As per Census 2011, Vadodara is the third populous city of Gujarat with a total population of 1, 839, 428.

Vadodara's weather is dry in nature. The climate of Vadodara is hot between the months of March and July. The maximum temperature of the city during these months is 40°C The minimum temperature in Vadodara is in the month of November to February which is 12°C . The climate in Vadodara becomes humid during the monsoon season. From mid-June to mid-September, the city experiences monsoon season. The average rainfall of Vadodara is recorded as 93 cm. Vadodara weather is also characterized by infrequent torrential rainfall that causes flood in the city. The heavy rainfall between June and September causes the river Vishwamitri, as well as the other rivers of Vadodara to flood.

SOURCES OF WATER SUPPLY

The main sources of water for the Vadodara city are the Sayaji Sarovar (Ajwa) on the northeast and Mahi river on the northwest of the city. On an average, VMC draws 45-50 MLD from Sayaji Sarovar. The present raw water delivery system is capable of transmitting 45-50 MLD of discharge by gravity to the Nimeta water treatment plant (WTP). The average per capita water supply is around 183 lpcd with a daily supply for 45 minutes twice a day. Tube wells are an alternate source of water supply in VMC. The water from these tube wells is directly injected into the distribution system. Depending upon the area served, the tube wells work from 1 to 18 hours everyday. Based on the capacity of pumps and working hours, the water supplied is believed to be 10 MLD from about 46 tube wells. These well operate in the areas where the water could not be supplied due to pressure problems. Due to the low drawl from these tube wells, the water table in the city does not get impacted. The average water table in the city is around 20 metres and gets recharged regularly due to the presence of perennial rivers in the north. Besides these tube wells, a series of 56 tube wells in the riverbed and around the banks of Mahi have been under development. In all, about 56 tube wells have been sunk. Of these, about 40 wells located on the bank are in working condition with submersible/turbine pumps already installed and commissioned. These tube wells are used in case of shortage of surface water. With the help of these wells, VMC has been tiding over the current water crisis in the last couple of years especially during draught situations.

SOURCE AND QUANTITY OF WATER SUPPLY

The city of Vadodara gets its water supply from various sources. The details of the sources of water supply for the city and the approximate quantities from them have been given in Table 1.

Table 1 Sources of water supply

Source Of Supply	Approximate Supply
Mahi Radial Collector Wells	100-120 MLD
Mahi River Tube Wells	55-65 MLD
Ajwa Mimeta	65-70 MLD
City Tube Wells	10-15 Mld
Total Supply	240-270 MLD

GEOHYDROLOGICAL ZONES OF VADODARA CITY

Geohydrology it is recent to sub recent alluvium formation comprises of alluvium Sand, clay, silt, gravel etc) with alternate clay, sand, silt gravel etc. Ground Water Conditions of Vadodara City is highly complicated from geohydrological point of view. The areas has great variations in aquifer thickness. From the geohydrological point of view, the city can be divided in to different zones depending upon the feasible depth of exploration and possibilities for creation of recharge structures in the area. Table 2 shows the various geohydrological zones of Vadodara city. The same have also been shown in Figure 1.

Table 2 Geo-hydrological zones of Vadodara city

Sr No	Area	Zone
1	Alkapuri, Gotri, Sevasi	I
2	Old padara Road, Akota, Atladara	II
3	Manjalpur, Makarpura, Pratnagar	III
4	Ajwa Road, Waghodia Road, Dabhoi Road, Warshia Ring Road, Harni Karelibaug, Harni Road.	IV
5	Subhanpura, Gorwa, IPCL, Refinery area	V
6	Fatehgunj, Nizampura, Sama, Savli Road, Chhani road	VI
7	City, Mandvi, Nyaymandir, Wadi, Fatehpura, Raopura, Panigate.	Mix

Figure 1 Geo-hydrological zones of Vadodara city

Geohydrological Zones of Vadodara City (As per the Aquifer System) :

The city can be divided in to seven zones as per the aquifer system. The city has very good aquifer system which is good for exploration as well as recharge, while it has non productive saline aquifers which is not good for exploration as well as the recharge. The detailed zones are described in the table below.

Sr No	Area	Zone	Feasible Depth (Mtr)	Aquifer Thickness (Mtr)	Remark
1	Alkapuri	I	50.00 to 70.00	25.00 to 30.00	Very good for recharge as aquifer characteristic is good fine to medium
2	Gotri, Sevasi	I	70.00 to 100.00	30.00 to 35.00	Very good for recharge structure, permeability deep aquifers.
3	Old padara Road, Akota, Atladara	II	30.00 to 50.00	20.00 to 25.00	Low yield area aquifers are mixed type with low intake capacity.
4	Manjalpur, Makarpura, Pratnagar	III	35.00 to 65.00	20.00 to 25.00	Good aquifers below 30 mt for recharge productive aquifer having good intake capacity.
5	Ajwa Road, Waghodia Road, Dabhoi Road, Warshia Ring Road, Harni Karelibaug, Harni Road.	IV	30.00 to 50.00	15.00 to 25.00	Non feasible for groundwater Exploration. Non-productive aquifers and saline zone. Sand and clay mixed zone.
6	Subhanpura, Gorwa, IPCL	V	55.00 to 60.00	25.00 to 30.00	Aquifers are good for recharge
7	Fatehgunj, Nizampura, Sama, Savli Road, Chhani road	VI	35.00 to 70.00	15.00 to 25.00	Non productive aquifers with dry aquifers but medium to coarse sand mixed with clay saline zone
8	City, Mandvi, Nyaymandir, Wadi, Fatehpura, Raopura, Panigate.	Mix	25.00 to 50.00	15.00 to 30.00	Highly non-productive saline aquifers at shallow depth. Only unconfined aquifers can be recharge through rooftop harvesting. Unconfined aquifers within 21.00 mt depth can be recharged by roof top harvesting.

Geohydrological Zones of Vadodara City (As per Hydrological Parameters) :

The city can also be divided into seven zones as per the hydrological parameters are concerned. The exploration varies between 60 LPM to 600 LPM as far as the city is concerned which is highly variant. The quality of the ground water in the city again is also different for different areas. The TDS varies from 1000 to more than 2000 PPM. The city can be divided into the zones as described in the bellowed table :

Sr No	Area	Zone	Nature Of Aquifer	Hydrological Parameters				
				S.W.L Mt.	P.W.L Mt.	D.D Mt.	Discharge in LPM	TDS Range In PPM
1	Alkapuri	I	Medium to fine	14 To 15	30 To 35	15	160 To 200	1000 To 1600
2	Gotri, Sevasi	I	Medium to fine	30 To 40	50 To 60	20 To 25	250 To 600	1200 To 1800
3	Old padara Road, Akota, Atladara	II	Fine Clay mixed	14 To 25	25 To 30	20 To 25	80 To 120	1500 To 2500
4	Manjalpur, Makarpura, Pratnagar	III	Mixed type aquifer with med sand	18 To 20	40 To 45	20 To 25	100 To 360	1500 To 2000
5	Ajwa Road, Waghodia Road, Dabhoi Road, Warshia Ring Road, Harni Karelibaug, Harni Road.	IV	Highly clay mixed non aquifer of saline	10 To 15	25 To 35	15 To 20	50 To 100	2000 and above
6	Subhanpura, Gorwa, IPCL	V	Fine to medium	18 To 20	50 To 60	30 To 35	120 To 500	1000 To 1200
7	Fatehgunj, Nizampura, Sama, Savli Road, Chhani road	VI	Mixed type of aquifers fine to medium	20 To 25	30 To 40	10 To 15	80 To 120	
8	City, Mandvi, Nyaymandir, Wadi, Fatehpura, Raopura, Panigate.	Mix	Mixed type non predictive aquifers sand, clay & kanker mixed	10 To 15	20 To 30	10 To 15	60 To 100	1000 To 2000

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION :

The study of geo hydrological condition is very important as far as the exploration and recharge of the ground water is concerned. The study needs special attention to the city like Vadodara which is highly complicated. Some of the areas are having good aquifers which is good for exploration and recharge, but some of the areas are having non productive saline aquifers which is not good for exploration as well as recharge. Again some of the areas like alkapuri, subhanpura etc. are having good quality of water while some areas like Ajwa Road, Waghodia Road etc. have saline water.

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